

Minutes EB24-03
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
17 September 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK-)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

None.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- 1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed.
- 2. FV to contact Sabine van Wegen to ask for a reminder to be sent to Community members on the vote for the SeqCode amendments.*
Completed.
- 3. All EB members to provide feedback on the ISME round table discussion document to MC by 8 July.*
Completed, see feedback of ISME round table under specific agenda item.
- 4. FV to contact Thulani Makhalenyane to discuss the promotion of the SeqCode at regional ISME meetings. Offer the possibility of virtual tutorials on how to use the Registry.*
Suggestion was that FV will contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
- 5. LMR with the assistance of Emily St John to start with the preparation of materials to demonstrate the use of the SeqCode registry at meetings.*
LMR busy preparing material which will first be used at the Chinese Microbial Ecology meeting in October. The Department of Neo-Latin at the University of Innsbruck is assisting with a video to explain the creation of acceptable Latin taxon names. This will be launched during a BISMIS Live event in 2025.
- 6. MC enquire about the SeqCode becoming a member of the DSI network.*
The DSI Network membership is only available for individuals. MC has registered and will inform the EB of any relevant information shared with her.

7. All EB members to familiarise themselves with RocketChat and to contribute to the discussion thread on the use of an isolate as a paratype in the SeqCode.

The discussion on paratypes will continue on RocketChat.

8. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.

KK will report when he has additional information.

9. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten after the formal report has been submitted.

Linda Scholten has informed the EB that funding for the SeqCode will now be processed according to the general ISME policy. The current funding will be for 2023 and 2024. An application for funding for 2025 needs to be submitted to ISME early in 2025. Payment for 2024 will only be processed once a short final report, which will be posted on the ISME website, has been submitted. LMR will finalize the 2024 funding report and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.

10. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot to amend the SeqCode and share it with the EB.

The results have been compiled. Of the 64 members who participated, 55 supported the amendments, 2 rejected the amendments and 7 opted to abstain.

11. LMR to follow-up on the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

The SeqCode registry is now linked.

12. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode.

Redacted

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The ballot dealing with changes to the SeqCode has been finalized. The outcome will be shared with the SeqCode Community (as above). It was decided that no formal publication will be necessary. IS will update and Version 1.1.0 of the SeqCode will now be posted on the Registry and ISME websites, as per the Statutes.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report. The working group was asked to discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries. The current policy dealing with metadata is already explained as part of the FAQ on the Registry website.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 585 names have been validated and another 249 have been endorsed. These names have been published in around 30 different journals which is indicative of uptake by the larger microbiology community. It is suggested that a report on the success of the Registry be published as part of the mid-term and final report of the current EB.

The working group is finalizing an internal policy on how to deal with incomplete entries. It was agreed that authors will be asked to respond within a month after being contacted. Afterwards no guarantee can be given that names will still be protected.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will have a meeting in the near future to discuss any possible issues.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

FV reported that after a number of minor changes, voting on the proposed changes to the ICNP has been initiated and would be completed by 4 December. In the case that the proposed rules are accepted, SeqCode names can be pre-validated by submission for inclusion on Candidatus lists. We should alert the community that for this to happen, the etymology and protologue should be published as part of the main text of the paper and not Supplementary Material.

6. Report on ISME roundtable

The roundtable held during the ISME 19 conference in Cape Town was well attended. Various issues were discussed such as the quality of genomes, replacement of type genomes in case of the availability of a better-quality genome and AI tools to assist with the creation of Latin names for taxa. The audience expressed their appreciation for the work done by the various SeqCode committees and working groups.

It was suggested that the EB initiates a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed. It was suggested to ask Marike Palmer and Casey Hubert from Canada to assist the EB.

7. EB discussion to move to Rocket Chat

The policy related to the use of RocketChat has changed and there is a restriction on the number of people who can participate on the free version. The EB decided that the SeqCode Community discussion will remain on Slack.

8. SeqCode presence on social media

FV will investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn. The creation of a Wikipedia page will also be investigated.

9. Conference and Meeting Updates

LMR will upload the ISME poster dealing with the Registry on the drive. FV will also upload a paper on the "Options and considerations for validation of prokaryotic names under the SeqCode" which was accepted for publication in the SeqCode special issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology.

Redacted

New action items

- 1.** FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
- 2.** FV to circulate the outcome of the ballot on changes to the SeqCode and have it posted on the ISME and Registry websites.
- 3.** FV to contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
- 4.** LMR to finalize the 2024 report on ISME funding and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.
- 5.** The EB to prepare a request for ISME funding in 2025 and submit it early in the new year.

6. IS to prepare SeqCode Version 1.1.0 and organise its posting on the Registry and ISME websites.
7. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.
8. FV to investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn.
9. FV to investigate the creation of a Wikipedia page for the SeqCode
10. BW to contact Marike Palmer to ask her to lead a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. EB members to participate in the discussion on paratypes on RocketChat.

Minutes prepared by FV: 20 September 2024

Approved: 28 September 2024